

The field experiment was conducted during Jan-Mar 1988 (mean daylength 11 h 55 min) in acid soils (pH 5.0) of CSRC Karamana (11°N, 77°E and 30 m above mean sea level). The riverine alluvium, sandy clay loam soil contained 0.7% organic C and 100-7-10 ppm of available NPK with an EC of 0.3 dS/m.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with eight

replications. The crops were broadcast in Jan 1988 at 30 kg seed/ha. No fertilizers were applied. One irrigation was given at sowing for germination.

Plant stands were uniform in all plots. Dry matter (DM) production and N yield were estimated using standard procedures at 50, 60, and 70 d after sowing (DAS).

S. rostrata had the highest DMP and

N yields at all three growth stages. At 50, 60, and 70 DAS, *S. rostrata* produced 5.0, 6.1, and 7.3 t DM, yielding 96, 145, and 153 kg N/ha, respectively. *S. aculeata* produced 4.7, 5.9, and 6.9 t DM, yielding 85, 131, and 140 kg N. *C. juncea* produced 3.4, 5.3, and 6.3 t DM, yielding 68, 110, and 122 kg N/ha. □

Disease management

Conidia release and dispersal pattern of *Pyricularia oryzae* under cloudy or rainy conditions

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We studied conidia release patterns from discrete blast lesions during 1988 rainy season in Korea, using a KY-type spore trap. On 13-14 Jul, it rained from 12 noon to 10 a.m. Conidia were released the entire time, with two distinct peaks between 1 and 7 a.m. (Fig. 1).

The first peak, 1-3 a.m., was due to the production of conidia from pre-existing conidiophores; the second peak, at 7 a.m., was due to conidia produced from conidiophores formed since 13 Jul evening. The peaks came by chance immediately after more than 16 mm rainfall/h. More conidia were released from 7-d-old lesions.

We also observed conidia dispersal under rainy conditions 21-22 Jul, using a rotary spore trap (Fig. 2). Usually conidia dispersal during rainfall of more than 3.5 mm/h is negligible, but in this experiment conidia dispersal was observed regardless of rainfall intensity. We believe that most of the conidia released and dispersed during rainy, cloudy conditions might be important as inoculum for blast epidemics. □

1. *P. oryzae* conidia release pattern under rainy conditions in Suweon, Korea, 13-14 Jul 1988.

2. *P. oryzae* conidia and dispersal pattern in Suweon, Korea, 21-22 Jul 1988.

Yield loss due to rice blast (BI) disease at different crop stages

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In 1984, leaf and panicle BI caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. occurred extensively in Thailand. We conducted field experiments at Pathum Thani Rice Research Center during dry and wet seasons 1986 to determine rice yield loss to BI at different crop stages.

Rice variety RD23 was direct sown in an 800-m² field and 513 sample units marked by binding units of approximately 10 tillers each with a string. Infected leaf area on each sample unit was estimated 45, 60, and 75 d after sowing (DAS).

All sample units were harvested and threshed separately and grain yield adjusted to 14% moisture content.

Data for each crop stage were grouped into classes of similar disease severity levels and average severity and average yield for each group calculated (Table 1). Average yield of group 1 was used to calculate yield loss of all other groups for a particular stage. Regression analysis was conducted on these new data sets.

All three, functions presented in Table 2 show a high statistical precision. BI

Table 1. Leaf Bl severity at different rice crop stages. Pathum Thani Rice Research Center, Thailand, 1986.

Observation	Disease severity (%)							
	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 5	Group 6	Group 7	Group 8
	<i>Wet season</i>							
45 DAS	0-0.05	1	2	3	5-8	10		
60 DAS	0-0.05	1	2	3	5	8-10	15-20	25-30
75 DAS	0-0.05	1	2-3	5	8-10	15	20	30
	<i>Dry season</i>							
45 DAS	0-0.05	1	2	3	5-8	10	15	
60 DAS	0-0.05	1	2	3	5-8	10	15	20-25
75 DAS	0-0.05	1	2	3	5-8	10	15	20-30

Table 2. Relationship between leaf Bl severity and yield loss (\hat{y}), derived from pooled data of two seasons. Pathum Thani Rice Research Center, Thailand, 1986.

Predictor variable ^a	Regression function	F ^b	R ²
BLA 45 DAS	$\hat{y} = 31.18 + 18.54 \ln(x)$	121.2***	0.92
BLA 60 DAS	$\hat{y} = 9.38 + 2.99x$	116.3***	0.89
BLA 75 DAS	$\hat{y} = 0.06 + 3.08x$	355.1***	0.96

^aBLA 45 DAS = % leaf area infected at 45 days after sowing. ^b*** P < 0.001.

severity during the reproductive stage (75 DAS) was most closely related to yield loss. Based on the third function,

1% infected leaf area corresponds to 3% yield loss. □

Estimating yield loss to rice blast (Bl) disease

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Rice yield loss equivalents for leaf and neck Bl found in earlier experiments had to be derived from multiple regression functions, because of mixed infection by several diseases. We conducted a field experiment to study the effect on yield of Bl alone.

RD23 was direct sown 20 Aug 1986 at Pathum Thani Rice Research Center. A source of inoculum was provided near the experimental plot. Ten 0.5-m² plots were staked out in an area 800 m². Incidence and severity of rice Bl was observed two times, at maximum tillering (60 d after sowing [DAS]) and 1 wk before harvest. Data were collected on percentage leaf area infected, number of tillers, number of panicles, number of

Linear regression between leaf Bl percentage and percent yield loss at Pathum Thani Research Center, 1986 wet season.

panicles with neck Bl, filled grain weight, and empty grain weight.

Sample plots showed 0-70% infected leaf area. Neck Bl incidence was 11-35%. Leaf Bl severity was not correlated with neck Bl incidence ($r = 0.233$ ns).

Yield of the plot free of leaf or neck Bl symptoms was used to calculate percentage yield loss in the other plots. Linear regression analysis resulted in a model to predict percentage yield loss from leaf Bl severity (see figure). The regression accounts for 78% of the variability in yield loss. □

Reaction of four rice cultivars to grassy stunt virus (GSV) strain 2 under natural conditions

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During wet season 1988 (Jun-Jul to Oct-Nov), a severe outbreak of GSV in parts of Kuttanad, Kerala, caused severe damage to the rice crop. Serological tests at Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad, confirmed that the outbreak was caused by GSV strain 2. We evaluated MO 5, MO 6, KAU153-1, and KAU93 for resistance to this strain under three levels of fertilizer, in a split-plot design with three replications. Disease incidence was scored just before panicle initiation.

MO 5, MO 6, and KAU153-1 were moderately susceptible; KAU93 was susceptible (see table). □

Resistance of rice varieties to GSV strain 2. Kerala, India, 1988 wet season.

Cultivar	Parentage	GSV damage (0-9)
MO 5	IR11-1-66/Kochuvithu	5
MO 6	IR8/Karivennel	5
KAU153-1	IR1561/Ptb 33	4
KAU93	Jaya/Ptb 33	7

Control of blast (Bl) in main field and nursery with some new fungicides

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Bl causes considerable yield losses in Nellore District under favorable weather conditions from Oct to Feb. We tested seven EC/WP and four granular fungicides to control leaf and neck Bl in transplanted rice in wet seasons (Oct-Feb) 1985-86, using highly susceptible IR50.

Plots were laid out in a randomized block design with four replications.